

Leveraging Feature Selection To Detect Potential Tax Fraudsters

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Abstract

Tax evasion is any act that knowingly or unknowingly, legally or unlawfully, leads to non-payment or underpayment of tax due. Enforcing the correct payment of taxes by taxpayers is fundamental in maintaining investments that are necessary and benefits a society as a whole. Indeed, without taxes it is not possible to guarantee basic services such as health-care, education, sanitation, transportation, infrastructure, among other services essential to the population. This issue is especially relevant in developing countries such as Brazil. In this work we consider a real-world case study involving the Treasury Office of the State of Ceará (SEFAZ-CE, Brazil), the agency in charge of supervising more than 300,000 active taxpayers companies. SEFAZ-CE maintains a very large database containing vast amounts of information concerning such companies. Its enforcement team struggles to perform thorough inspections on taxpayers accounts as the underlying traditional human-based inspection processes involve the evaluation of countless fraud indicators (i.e., binary features), thus requiring burdensome amounts of time and being potentially prone to human errors. On the other hand, the vast amount of taxpayer information collected by fiscal agencies opens up the possibility of devising novel techniques able to tackle

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fiscal evasion much more effectively than traditional approaches. In this work we address the problem of using feature selection to select the most relevant binary features to improve the classification of potential tax fraudsters. Finding out possible fraudsters from taxpayer data with binary features presents several challenges. First, taxpayer data typically have features with low linear correlation between themselves. Also, tax frauds may originate from intricate illicit tactics, which in turn requires to uncover non-linear relationships between multiple features. Finally, few features may be correlated with the targeted class. In this work we propose ALICIA, a new feature selection method based on association rules and propositional logic with a carefully crafted graph centrality measure that attempts to tackle the above challenges while, at the same time, being agnostic to specific classification techniques. ALICIA is structured in three phases: first, it generates a set of relevant association rules from a set of fraud indicators (features). Subsequently, from such association rules ALICIA builds a graph, which structure is then used to determine the most relevant features. To achieve this ALICIA applies a novel centrality measure we call the *Feature Topological Importance*. We perform an extensive experimental evaluation to assess the validity of our proposal on four different real-world datasets, where we compare our solution with eight other feature selection methods. The results show that ALICIA achieves F-measure scores up to 76.88%, and consistently outperforms its competitors.

Keywords: Feature selection, Tax Fraud Detection, Association Rules, Graph Centrality Measure

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1. Introduction

In Brazil, one of the major problems in tax management is tax evasion. Ensuring that taxpayers pay their taxes due allows to sustain investments that are necessary for a modern and functional society. Indeed, without taxes it is not possible to guarantee health-care, education, sanitation, transportation, infras-

structures, among other services essential to the population. In general terms tax evasion can be defined as an act that knowingly or unknowingly, legally or unlawfully, leads to non-payment or underpayment of tax due. The type of tax evasion addressed in this paper is *tax fraud*. In general terms tax fraud can be defined as any action or omission practiced with deceit, cunning, malice or bad faith, that seeks to reduce or eliminate tax due on some chargeable entity (e.g., products, services, events, and so on). In this paper we call *taxpayers*¹ who practice any type of tax fraud as *tax fraudster*.

Tax frauds represent one of the major obstacles faced by the economies of developing countries. In the recent past, several initiatives were undertaken to develop applications that collect and leverage taxpayer information to detect tax fraudsters [NFE \(2019\)](#); [CTE \(2019\)](#); [SPED \(2019\)](#); [MDFE \(2019\)](#). The amount of frauds, however, is still very high – for instance, the level of tax evasion in Brazil proved to be about 90 billions US\$ in 2018². These numbers show that reducing tax evasion is paramount for any fiscal system. This scenario opens up to the possibility of devising novel algorithms that can be used to tackle tax evasion much more effectively than traditional human-based approaches.

Several Brazilian Finance Departments are focusing on expert systems to aid and enhance decision making. Among the decisions that a tax administration has to deal with, one of the most important is undoubtedly knowing *who to inspect* or who needs *greater tax control*. Machine Learning (ML) thus represents an extremely important set of tools for those organizations that have large databases, with governmental organizations among these. Currently, the Finance Departments of the States of Brazil receive a large volume of data on the operations of companies, both registered in their systems or as information extracted from other sources.

¹We define a taxpayer to be an individual who pay taxes when purchasing products, services, or any other taxable event/item.

²<https://ibpt.com.br/noticia/2734/Brasil-deixou-de-arrecadar-R-345-bi-por-sonegacao-de-impostos> (retrieved: September 15, 2019)

In this work we consider a real-world case study involving the Treasury Office of the State of Ceará (SEFAZ-CE, Brazil)³, the agency in charge of supervising more than 300,000 active taxpayers companies in the state of Ceará, Brazil. SEFAZ-CE receives each month large volumes of data concerning the operations of such companies, as well as further information collected from other sources. Its enforcement team historically struggled to perform through inspections on taxpayers accounts, as the traditional inspection processes employ human-based evaluation of countless fraud indicators (i.e., binary features). Indeed, these require burdensome amounts of time and are potentially prone to human errors. This research considers the taxpayers of industry, commerce and services taxed by the ICMS (Imposto sobre Circulação de Mercadorias e Serviços or Tax on Commerce and Services). The ICMS is a tax covering the circulation of goods and services involving transport and communications dos Santos et al. (2017). The share of taxes collected from the ICMS represents alone, on average, the 95% of taxes collected by Brazilian states. As such, we argue that this work is relevant in strengthening the ability of Brazilian states to maintain good levels of revenue and, consequently, investments for the community. The most frequent types of tax frauds observed in collecting the ICMS are income under-reporting, use of fake/adulterated documents, and the production of false statements.

With the application of ML techniques, the problem of focusing on the most relevant information has become very important and far easier to solve. Thus, one of the main problems in ML is the selection of relevant features, a well-known problem known as *feature selection*. There are several reasons behind solving such problem. One of these reasons is that the most computationally viable ML algorithms do not work well in the presence of a large number of features, thus feature selection can improve the accuracy of classifiers. Another reason is that the selection of features improves the human’s ability to understand the data and also, for example, the rules of induction generated by symbolic ML algorithms. A third reason to employ feature selection is the high cost to

³<http://www.sefaz.ce.gov.br/>

acquire the features information, since in many domains the collection of data can be very expensive. Finally, feature selection can reduce the processing costs of large amounts of data.

In general terms, Feature Selection can be described in terms of a process that selects a subset of *relevant* features, among those available, to be subsequently used to build learning models. Many existing feature selection techniques focus on selecting feature subsets that are strongly correlated with some class; in the context of tax fraud detection, however, there is a need to find out and leverage relationships between features, as frauds may originate from complex, illicit tactics. As we will see throughout this work, classification methods employed to detect potential tax fraudsters *without* the use of feature selection do not achieve results better than 58% of F-measure. The use of *traditional* feature selection methods do yield better results, i.e., up to 70% of F-measure, however better detection performance is called for. Thus, the problem of selecting an effective and more representative feature set in detecting tax fraudsters needs more effective solutions and this is the goal of our work.

One common practice for feature selection is to simply select the top-ranked fraud indicators (i.e., binary features) based on linear correlation. One major limitation of such simple ranking approach is its inability to deal with features that have low or no correlation; moreover, it is not uncommon that only a small number of such features show some correlation with the targeted class. Indeed, these features are typically not good enough to perform a satisfactory classification because they tend to produce noise to the classification task, thus decreasing the final accuracy.

1.1. Research Problems

Several data mining techniques have been extensively used to detect financial frauds [Ravisankar et al. \(2011\)](#); [Glancy & Yadav \(2011\)](#); [Kirkos et al. \(2007\)](#), insurance frauds [Ngai et al. \(2011\)](#), credit card frauds [Bhattacharyya et al. \(2011\)](#); [Sánchez et al. \(2009\)](#), fraudulent transactions [Li et al. \(2012\)](#); [Phua et al. \(2010\)](#), and e-commerce frauds [Zhang et al. \(2013\)](#); [Kim et al. \(2013\)](#); [Richhariya et al.](#)

(2012). These approaches, however, do not exploit *feature selection* to reduce the number of features considered. Considered the sheer amount of indicators that can be used to characterize fraudsters, feature selection represents a powerful pre-processing tool to reduce the cost of feature measurement, speed up the testing process, and increase the efficiency and accuracy of classifiers [Kira & Rendell \(1992b\)](#); [Kohavi & John \(1997a\)](#).

The main goal of this work is to introduce a novel feature selection method in the context of tax fraudster detection. In this work we address some challenges not considered in the available literature:

- 100 1. Tax fraud indicators (binary features) have low or non-linear correlation between themselves. The ability to capture these relationships can improve the performance of feature selection methods.
2. Typically, only a small number of these features show some correlation with the targeted class.
- 105 3. All features and classes are binary.

Consequently, we focus on the following *research question*: how do we select the most appropriate subset of binary features having (i) *low or non-linear correlation* between themselves and that (ii) are possibly *non informative* for the target class, with the final objective of improving the classification of potential tax fraudsters?

To address the research question above we propose a novel feature selection ranking method called ALICIA. The key idea behind ALICIA is to combine association rules and propositional logic with graph centrality measure to capture the hidden relationship between tax fraud indicators. In other words, ALICIA leverages association rules and a carefully crafted graph centrality measure to identify the most relevant features for tax fraudsters classification. ALICIA is structured in three phases: in the first phase the approach generates a set of relevant fraud association rules from tax fraud data, where taxpayers are associated with a set of fraud indicators (binary features). Still in this phase we also introduce the notion of dependency structures in association rules as a

tool that can be used to possibly capture even more relevant association rules. Subsequently ALICIA builds a graph, where nodes represent subsets of features present in the association rules, while edges represent the association rules between the subsets. Finally, ALICIA evaluates the importance associated with the nodes of the graph according to a novel graph centrality measure, and returns
125 the final relevance ranking of the features.

To assess the quality of our proposal we conduct a performance comparison with eight, well-established feature selection methods: Information Gain (IG), Gain Ratio (GR), Correlation-based Feature Selection (CFS), Feature Selection
130 via Eigenvector Centrality(ECFS), Relief-F, Fisher, Gradient boosted feature selection (GBFS) and XGBoost Feature Importance (XGB-FI). We use three different real-world datasets provided by SEFAZ-CE containing data of 300,000 taxpayer companies. The datasets cover a period of time comprised between 2009 and 2011. We also consider a public credit card dataset to prove ALICIA’s
135 capability of generalizing in other fraud contexts. The results show that ALICIA, coupled with an SVM-based classifier, achieves F-measure scores up to 76.88% and consistently outperforms its competitors.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides some background on the key topics underlying this work, i.e., feature selection, association rule learn-
140 ing, and graph centrality measures. Section 3 presents our proposal, ALICIA. Sections 4 and 5 present, respectively, the experimental setting and the experimental evaluation. Finally, Section 6 presents the related work, while Section 7 draws the final conclusions.

2. Background

145 In this section we provide an overview on the notions used throughout this work. Section 2.1 provides an overview on *feature selection*. Section 2.2 provides an overview on *association rule learning*. Finally, Section 2.3 provides an overview on *node centrality* measures.

2.1. Feature selection

150 When considering the problem of detecting tax frauds, using a high number
of features does not necessarily translate into a high classification accuracy and
it may require too many computational resources. To this end, feature selection
methods can be used as a pre-processing tool to select features that are *relevant*
for the problem considered. In general terms, these methods aim at reducing
155 the number of *irrelevant* features while maintaining good classification accuracy.
We observe that feature selection methods are different than feature extraction
ones, since the latter create new features originating from the combination or
transformation of the initial features [Devijver & Kittler \(1982\)](#).

Feature selection methods consider two qualities of features regardless of
160 the specificity of individual approaches: *relevance* and *redundancy* [Yu & Liu \(2004\)](#).
A feature is said to be *relevant* if it cannot be removed from the set to
which it belongs to, without affecting its original conditional class distribution.
A feature is said to be *redundant* if it is highly correlated with other features.
To this end, it is important to note that features that may be irrelevant when
165 considered singularly may become relevant when considered in combination with
other features.

In general, using a good feature selection method can increase classification
accuracy with respect to other strategies [Kira & Rendell \(1992b\)](#); [Kohavi &
John \(1997a\)](#). Determining an optimal subset of relevant features is challenging,
170 as there is often a trade-off between two possibly competing goals. The first
one is to achieve *minimality*, i.e., minimize the number of relevant features
returned by the selection method. The second one is to achieve *suitability*, i.e.,
returning a subset of features that maximize accuracy. A proper trade-off is
usually domain-dependent. In light of the above considerations we introduce
175 the following problem statement.

Definition 2.1 (Feature Selection Problem). Given a feature set F , we
define the problem of *feature selection* as the problem of finding out a *near
optimal* subset of features $M \subseteq F$ among the competing $2^{|F|}$ candidate subsets.

The definition of optimality may vary according to the specificity of the scenario
180 considered. Additionally, naive (brute-force) approaches are typically unfeasible
with most datasets, as the candidate space grows exponentially in the number
of features. Consequently, feature selection methods try to exploit some kind of
heuristic to effectively reduce the search space and find near-optimal solutions
Dash & Liu (1997); Ruiz et al. (2005). Existing feature selection methods fall
185 under three categories: *filter*, *wrapper* and *embedded*, where the categorization
stems from the different strategies used to *measure* the optimality of subsets of
features Guyon & Elisseeff (2003).

Filter methods determine the optimality of subsets of features by focusing
on their intrinsic properties – indeed, these methods employ uni-variate statis-
190 tics rather than trying to maximize the accuracy of some classification model.
This allows to separate the problem of feature selection from that of optimizing
classifier performance, which in turn avoids the need to perform repeated and
expensive model training steps. Filter methods use statistical properties charac-
terizing features to *score* and *rank* subsets of features, independently of specific
195 learning algorithms used Chandrashekar & Sahin (2014); Liu & Motoda (2007).
Note that some filter methods (e.g., those based on mutual information criteria)
provide a generic approach to select relevant features, hence they may be not
suitable for some machine learning methods. Filter methods can be employed as
a pre-processing tool too, to reduce space dimensionality and avoid over-fitting.
200 These methods typically use all the training data to look for relevant subsets of
features and are generally less prone to over-fitting.

Wrapper methods determine the optimality of subsets of features according
to the *accuracy* of a given classifier. In general, this allows to achieve greater
accuracy than filter methods at the expense of far greater computational costs
205 due to the need of training multiple models Kohavi & John (1997b). Finally,
embedded methods Lal et al. (2006) are structurally similar to wrapper meth-
ods, with the notable difference that the expected risk functions used to train
classification models incorporate information concerning the set of considered
features.

210 The approach we propose in this work, ALICIA, can be framed in the context
of filter methods. We thus compare our solution to other eight methods belong-
ing to the same category: Information Gain (IG) Liu & Motoda (2012), Gain
Ratio (GR) Liu & Motoda (2012); Karegowda et al. (2010), Correlation-based
Feature Selection (CFS) Hall (1999), Feature Selection via Eigenvector Central-
215 ity(ECFS) Roffo & Melzi (2016), Relief-F Kira & Rendell (1992a), Fisher Gu
et al. (2012), Gradient boosted feature selection (GBFS) Xu et al. (2014) and
XGBoost Feature Importance (XGB-FI) Chen & Guestrin (2016).

2.2. Association rule learning

The goal of association rule learning is to identify associations between data
220 records (items) that are *related*. To achieve this goal the key idea is to find
subsets of items which presence is *correlated* with the presence of some other
item(s) in the same transaction. Apriori Agrawal & Srikant (1994) represents
an association rule technique widely used in market basket analysis, cross mar-
keting, and customer buying pattern. Association rule techniques represent
225 promising tools in the context of fraud detection, since they can be used to dis-
cover hidden relationships among various fraud features Sánchez et al. (2009);
Phua et al. (2010); Kim et al. (2013).

Definition 2.2 (Association rule). Let us suppose that $I = \{i_1, \dots, i_m\}$
represents a set of *items*. Then, an *association rule* represents an implication
230 of the form $X \rightarrow Y$, where $X, Y \subseteq I$ and $X \cap Y = \emptyset$.

Association rules are incrementally derived from a set of transactions D .
Their “importance” is measured in terms of *support* and *confidence* Agrawal &
Srikant (1994). Let us denote by $N = |D|$ the overall number of transactions
in D . Then, the *support* of an association rule $X \rightarrow Y$, and we denote it by
 $\sigma(X \rightarrow Y)$, is the number of transactions where the itemset $Z = X \cup Y$ appears.
Formally:

$$\text{supp}(X \rightarrow Y) = \frac{\sigma(X \cup Y)}{N} \quad (1)$$

The *confidence* of an association rule expresses how frequently the item(s) in Y appear(s) in transactions that contain X . Formally:

$$conf(X \rightarrow Y) = \frac{\sigma(X \cup Y)}{\sigma(X)} \quad (2)$$

Finally, the *lift* of an association rule represents a correlation measure between itemsets that can be used to augment the *support-confidence* framework Han & Kamber (2006):

$$lift(X \rightarrow Y) = \frac{\sigma(X \cup Y)}{\sigma(X) \cdot \sigma(Y)} \quad (3)$$

In general, $lift(X \rightarrow Y) < 1$ indicates that the occurrence of X is negatively correlated with the occurrence of Y (i.e., the lower the lift, the more the occurrence of X implies the occurrence of Y). $lift(X \rightarrow Y) > 1$ represents the symmetric case. Finally, $lift(X \rightarrow Y) = 1$ indicates the absence of correlation
235 between X and Y , i.e., the two itemsets are independent.

2.3. Node centrality measures

The main goal of node centrality measures is to capture the *importance* that individual nodes have within a graph Freeman (1977). In general, central nodes are interesting since they have three characteristics that set them apart from
240 other nodes: they possess more edges (relationships), their average distance to other nodes is lower, and they possess a major role in regulating the flow between nodes of the graph.

Considering the ubiquity of graphs, the concept of centrality is investigated in a relevant number of domains Opsahl & Panzarasa (2009); Barrat et al.
245 (2004); Doreian et al. (2005), including feature selection Moradi & Rostami (2015); Bonev et al. (2013); Zhang et al. (2011). Indeed, feature selection has been used in the past to rank single features. However, in most datasets features are not independent and combining them provides much more information than considering them individually. As such, feature subset selection can be
250 conducted by exploiting some graph centrality measure to capture relationships between nodes of a graph.

In the context of this work we consider three different measures of centrality Freeman (1978), i.e., *degree* centrality, *closeness* centrality, and *betweenness* centrality.

255 3. Leveraging feature selection to detect potential tax fraudsters

In this section we introduce ALICIA, a new feature selection method that aims at answering the research challenges highlighted in Section 1. The key idea behind ALICIA is to combine association rules, propositional logic, and a carefully crafted *graph centrality measure* to capture hidden relationships (i.e., 260 non-linear correlations) between tax fraud indicators (features). The goal is to identify the most relevant features for tax fraudsters classification. Our method is structured in three phases – Algorithm 1 provides an overview.

In the first phase (GENERATERULES, line 2) ALICIA takes in input a data matrix S (i.e., a matrix where each row refers to a single taxpayer and each 265 column refers to a specific feature) to generate the set of association rules, *rules*. In the second phase, GENERATEGRAPH (line 3) ALICIA builds from *rules* the graph of association rules G , with each node representing a subset of features present in any of the association rules in *rules*, and each edge representing a specific association rule. In the third final phase (RANKFEATURES, line 4)

Algorithm 1: ALICIA

Input :

- S , the data matrix.
- $supp$, the support threshold to be used with Apriori.
- $conf$, the confidence threshold to be used with Apriori.
- $lift$, the lift threshold to be used with Apriori.
- n , the n-reachability threshold used when ranking the features.
- $maxFeatsVertex$, maximum number of features associated with a vertex.
- $dependency$, boolean to indicate the use of dependency in rules generation

```

1 begin
2    $rules \leftarrow GENERATERULES(S, supp, conf, lift, dependency)$            // Phase I
3    $G \leftarrow GENERATEGRAPH(rules)$                                      // Phase II
4    $KeyFeatures \leftarrow RANKFEATURES(G, n, maxNumFeatVertex)$          // Phase III
5   return  $KeyFeatures$ 

```

270 ALICIA computes the relevance ranking (in descending order) of the graph nodes,
 which is then used to establish the most relevant features. Such ranking is
 computed by means of a novel node centrality measure we call *Fraud Feature*
Topological Importance (F2TI).

In the following we provide the details behind each phase.

275 3.1. Phase I – Generating the set of relevant fraud association rules

The goal of the first phase, which we call GENERATERULES, is to produce
 a set of association rules. Algorithm 2 reports the associated high-level pseu-
 docode pseudocode. GENERATERULES takes in input a data matrix S , where
 a generic element $s_{i,j} \in S$ indicates whether the i -th taxpayer is associated
 280 (1) or not (0) with the j -th fraud indicator (feature). The algorithm takes
 also in input several thresholds that are used by the Apriori algorithm to com-
 pute the association rules: support (*supp*), confidence (*conf*), and *lift*. Finally,
 the input variable *dependency* indicates whether GENERATERULES should use
 dependency structures (we refer the reader to subsection 3.1.1) to generate fur-
 285 ther rules. GENERATERULES first computes from S the set of association rules,
 APR , using the Apriori algorithm (line 3). Subsequently, GENERATERULES
 prunes from APR the rules that have lift below the provided threshold (lines

Algorithm 2: GENERATERULES

Input :

- S , the data matrix.
- *supp*, the support threshold.
- *conf*, the confidence threshold.
- *lift*, the lift threshold.
- *dependency*, boolean to indicate the use of dependency

```

1 begin
2    $RARS \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3    $APR \leftarrow \text{Apriori}(S, \text{supp}, \text{conf})$ 
4   foreach  $ap \in APR$  do
5     if  $(\text{Lift}(ap) \geq \text{lift})$  then  $RARS \leftarrow RARS \cup \{ap\}$ 
6   if  $(\text{dependency} = \text{true})$  then  $RARS \leftarrow RARS \cup \text{GENERATEDDEPENDENCIES}(RARS)$ 
7   return  $RARS$ 

```

4–5), thus yielding the set $RARS$. Finally, if instructed to do so, GENERATERULES generates further rules by using the notion of *dependency structures* (function GENERATEDDEPENDENCIES, line 6). We provide more details on this optional step in Section 3.1.1.

3.1.1. Dependency structures of association rules

In the following we introduce an axiomatic description of dependency structures in association rules. The axioms specify those families of dependencies “A determines B” which can hold for some association rules in $RARS$. These dependencies allow the method we propose, ALICIA to possibly capture further rules that may have been missed by Apriori and that may improve the final feature selection quality. Leveraging on propositional logic [Krajicek et al. \(1995\)](#); [Fagin \(1977\)](#) in the following we propose a set of axioms that can be used to generate further rules from the ones within $RARS$.

Axiom of reflexivity. Let $RARS$ be a set of association rules. Let then A be a set of features used in some association rule $A \rightarrow Z \in RARS$. Let then $B \subseteq A$. Then $A \rightarrow B$ is true and added to $RARS$.

Axiom of composition. Let $RARS$ be a set of association rules. If $A \rightarrow B \in RARS$ and $A \rightarrow C \in RARS$, then $A \rightarrow BC$ is true and added to $RARS$.

Axiom of transitivity. Let $RARS$ be a set of association rules. If $A \rightarrow B \in RARS$ and $B \rightarrow C \in RARS$, then $A \rightarrow C$ is true and added to $RARS$.

The above axioms are used to augment $RARS$ and are applied as long as it is possible to generate new rules, either from those generated by Apriori, or those created afterwards by means of the axioms. While the generation of further rules does not represent a mandatory step, it represents an attempt to improve the final feature importance ranking (subsection 3.3), as also shown in Section 5.

Algorithm 3: GENERATEGRAPH

Input : $rules$, the set of relevant associative rules.

```
1 begin
2    $V \leftarrow \emptyset, E \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3   foreach  $(X \rightarrow Y) \in rules$  do
4     if  $X \not\subseteq V$  then  $V \leftarrow V \cup \{X\}$ 
5     if  $Y \not\subseteq V$  then  $V \leftarrow V \cup \{Y\}$ 
6     if  $(X, Y) \notin E$  then  $E \leftarrow E \cup (X, Y)$ 
7   return  $G = (V, E)$ 
```

3.2. Phase II – Building the graph of association rules

315 The goal of this phase is to build the directed graph of association rules G from the set of rules $rules$ computed in the first phase. We represent such phase by means of the function GENERATEGRAPH, for which Algorithm 3 reports the associated pseudocode. The algorithm begins by initializing the graph G , setting both V and E to an empty set (line 2). Subsequently, the association
320 rules available in $rules$ are used to build G . Specifically, for each association rule $X \rightarrow Y \in rules$ the algorithm creates (if not already present) two *nodes* representing the subsets of features appearing, respectively, on the left and right hand side of the rule. The algorithm creates also a *directed edge* (X, Y) , representing the rule associating the two subsets. GENERATEGRAPH terminates
325 once it has evaluated all the association rules, and returns the final graph G .

3.3. Phase III – Feature ranking

The goal of the last phase is to rank features starting from the information available in the graph of association rules. To this end we introduce a novel centrality measure, i.e., the *Fraud Feature Topological Importance* (F2TI) measure
330 (note that our measure borrows some ideas from Jordán et al. (2003)).

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph of association rules, and let $i \in V$ be some vertex in G : a node $v \in V$ is said to be *n-reachable* from i if the number of edges of the shortest path connecting i to v is *less or equal* than n . Let us also define $a_n(G, i, v)$ as the *influence* of i on any $v \in V$ that is *n-reachable* from i . We

then define $a_n(G, i, v)$ as:

$$a_n(G, i, v) = 1/D_n(G, i), \quad (4)$$

with $D_n(G, i)$ representing the number of vertices that are n -reachable from i .

Example: $a_4(G, i, v) = 1/8$ implies that i has $D_4(G, i) = 8$ vertices that are 4-reachable from it. The value implies also that any vertex $v \in V$ that is 4-reachable from i is subjected to i 's $a_4(G, i, v) = 1/8$ influence. 335

Finally, we define $\sigma_n(G, i)$ to be the *total n -step influence* of i , and is defined as the sum of i 's influence on every node that is n -reachable from it. Formally:

$$\sigma_n(G, i) = \sum_{v \in V} a_n(G, i, v) \quad (5)$$

At this point we can define the *Fraud Feature Topological Importance* (F2TI) centrality measure.

Definition 3.1 (Fraud Feature Topological Importance). Let $G = (V, E)$ be the graph of association rules and $n \geq 1$ be some n -reachability threshold. 340 Then, given a vertex $v \in V$, v 's *Fraud Feature Topological Importance* score is computed as follows:

$$F2TI(G, n, v) = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^n \sigma_m(G, v)}{\max(1, n - 1)}. \quad (6)$$

The intuition behind *F2TI* is to measure the importance of a node v by examining how “well” it is connected to other nodes in the graph, i.e., the more the nodes n -reachable from v , the more the v 's importance. 345

At this point it is possible to introduce the algorithm in charge of outputting the final feature ranking, `RANKFEATURES` (Algorithm 4). `RANKFEATURES` takes in input the graph of association rules $G = (V, E)$, the variable n representing the n -reachability criterion, and the variable `maxFeatsVertex`, 350 which represents the maximum number of features a vertex may have associated in order to be considered during this phase. First, `RANKFEATURES` initializes

Algorithm 4: RANKFEATURES

Input:

- $G = (V, E)$, the graph of association rules.
- n , the n -reachability threshold.
- $maxFeatsVertex$, maximum number of features in a vertex.

Output: The ranking of the features, $RankFeatures$

```
1 begin
2    $RankFeatures \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3    $V' \leftarrow getVertices(V, maxFeatsVertex)$ 
4   foreach  $v \in V'$  do
5      $SetFeaturesVertex \leftarrow getFeaturesVertex(v)$ 
6      $score \leftarrow \frac{F2TI(G, n, v)}{|SetFeaturesVertex|}$ 
7     foreach  $f \in SetFeaturesVertex$  do
8        $RankFeatures \leftarrow update(RankFeatures, (f, score))$ 
9   Sort features in  $RankFeatures$  according to the associated scores
10  return  $RankFeatures$ 
```

$RankFeatures$ to an empty set (line 2) and extracts from V the subset of vertices that are associated with up to $maxNumFeatVertex$ features (line 3) – we denote such subset by V' . Subsequently, for each vertex $v \in V'$ (line 4) RANKFEATURES determines the associated F2TI score and distributes it evenly across its features: more precisely, the algorithm first determines the subset of features associated with v (line 5), then computes the F2TI score divided by the number of features associated with v (line 6), and finally updates the score of each feature associated with v (line 7). The algorithm concludes by sorting the pairs $(feature, score)$ in $RankFeatures$ according to their score (line 8), thus yielding the final feature ranking. Note that the variable $maxFeatsVertex$ allows the user to choose a proper trade-off between the amount of information considered from the graph and the execution time that results from the complexity of the for cycle at line 7.

4. Experimental Setting

In this section we provide the experimental setting. More specifically, Section 4.1 introduces the dataset as well as the related data preparation. Section

4.2 provides the competitors, while Section 4.3 introduces the experimental methodology. Finally, Section 4.4 provides the parameters used at run-time with the various competitors.

4.1. Dataset and data preparation

In this work we consider two different kinds of dataset:

- Historical audit data covering an interval of time comprised between 2009 and 2011. The data is provided by the Treasury Office of the State of Ceará (SEFAZ-CE - Brazil) and covers more than 300,000 active taxpayers companies. From now on we denote such datasets by *TFM-2009*, *TFM-2010* and *TFM-2011*.
- Anonymized credit card transactions labeled as fraudulent or genuine. The datasets contains transactions made by credit cards in September 2013 by European cardholders. From here on, we denote this dataset *DS-CreditCard*.

For what concerns historical audit data, for each specific year we focus on specific subsets of *fraud indicators*, among those available, according to recommendations provided by expert tax auditors. More precisely, for data covering 2009 and 2010 we focus on a set of 14 features, while for data covering 2011 we focus on 16 features – in this context we note that features frequently change over the years, as fraudsters tend to evolve their strategies. Finally, we report that features and taxpayer identities are anonymized. Accordingly, we arrange the data in three different tax fraud matrices. Table 1 reports their main characteristics. In the matrices each row refers to a single taxpayer, while each column is associated with a specific fraud indicator (feature). As such, if $m_{i,j}$ represents a generic element of the matrices, we have that $m_{i,j} = 1$ if the i -th taxpayer committed the j -th fraud, $m_{i,j} = 0$ otherwise. Taxpayers who did not present any evidence of fraud were excluded (i.e., they were considered outliers).

The other dataset that we use to assess the validity of ALICIA contains

credit card transactions and is provided by Kaggle⁴. We denote such dataset by *DS-CreditCard*. The dataset contains transactions occurred during two distinct days, and features 492 frauds out of 284,807 transactions. The dataset is clearly highly unbalanced, as the positive class (frauds) accounts for only 0.172% of all transactions. The dataset contains only numerical features, which are the result of a PCA transformation Dal Pozzolo et al. (2015). Unfortunately, due to confidentiality issues, the original features and background information are not provided. Each transaction is associated with a set of 31 features. Features V1, V2, ... V28 are the principal components obtained with PCA; the only features which have not been transformed are *Time*, *Amount*, and *Class*. *Time* represents the seconds elapsed between each transaction and the first transaction in the dataset. *Amount* represents the amount of money involved in a transaction (such feature can be used for example-dependant cost-sensitive learning). Finally, the feature *Class* indicates whether a transaction is either illicit (1) or not (0).

4.2. Competitors

We compare ALICIA with the feature selection methods presented in Section 2.1, i.e., Information Gain (IG), Gain Ratio (GR), Correlation-based Feature Selection (CFS), Feature Selection via Eigenvector Centrality (ECFS), Relief-F, Fisher, and Gradient boosted feature selection (GBFS). To evaluate ECFS, Relief-F, and Fisher we use the *Feature Selection Code Library* (FSLib) Roffo

⁴<https://www.kaggle.com>

Dataset	Year covered	# features (columns)	# taxpayers (rows)
TFM-2009	2009	14	11,386
TFM-2010	2010	14	12,424
TFM-2011	2011	16	10,627

Table 1: Metadata of the tax fraud matrices considered in the experimental evaluation.

et al. (2017). To evaluate IG, GR and CFS we use the R package *FSelector* Romanski (2016). To evaluate GBFS we use the library provided by Xu (2018).

For what concerns the *DS-CreditCard* dataset we found out that the best
420 classification algorithm was *XGBoost*. *XGBoost* employs a native feature selection method called *XGBoost feature importance* (XGB-FI). As such, when dealing with this dataset we include XGB-FI in the comparison as well⁵.

4.3. Methodology

To assess the feature selection quality of the various competitors over the
425 *TFM-2009*, *TFM-2010* and *TFM-2011* datasets we employ the SVM-based classifier available in R Karatzoglou et al. (2004). On the other hand, when dealing with the *DS-CreditCard* dataset we use the *XGBoost* classifier available in Python *XGBoost - Python API reference* (2018).

Both classifiers are used to determine recall, precision and F-Measure as-
430 sociated with the results obtained by means of the features selected by the competitors. We also report the use of 10-fold cross-validation Kohavi et al. (1995), as it guarantees less biased estimations of accuracy.

4.4. Run-time parameters

When generating association rules ALICIA uses the following defaults for
435 the parameters involved: *supp* = 0.3, *conf* = 0.4 and *lift* = 1.3 – we report that these values were chosen according to an extensive experimental evaluation (which we report in Section 5). For what concerns the remaining parameters, the default *n*-reachability threshold is set to 10, while *maxFeaturesVertex* default value is set to 1. The SVM-based classifier employs a Radial Basis (Gaussian)
440 kernel, with γ varied in the $[10^{-6}, 10^{-1}]$ range and τ varied in the $[10^{-4}, 10^{-1}]$ range. The *XGBoost* classifier employs cross validation, which in turn involves a grid search. For such grid search we report the parameters and the associated ranges: *learning_rate* = [0.05, 0.1], *max_depth* = [6, 7, 8], *min_child_weight* =

⁵Source code is available at <https://github.com/rtales/kaggle-credit-card>.

[1, 10], and $n_estimators = [400, 500]$. Finally, to guarantee reproducibility we
445 report that we used a fixed seed equal to 100.

5. Experimental Evaluation

In the following we describe the results of the experimental evaluation. Section
5.1 presents an analysis covering the generation of association rules from
the considered datasets. Section 5.2 assesses the run-time performance of ALI-
450 CIA. Finally, Section 5.3 evaluates the quality of the feature selection performed
by the various competitors.

5.1. Analysis on the generation of association rules.

The quality of the results returned by association rule learning algorithms
depends on the properties of input data and on the choice of proper *support*,
455 *confidence*, and *lift* thresholds. The first parameter on which we focus our
attention is *support*, and we study how its distribution varies among the asso-
ciation rules generated from the considered datasets. In general, high support
thresholds yields the generation of *relevant* association rules, yet potentially
interesting rules involving infrequent features may be missed. Conversely, low
460 support thresholds overcome the above issue at the expense of possibly gener-
ating many *irrelevant* rules. Consequently, studying the support distribution
allows us to find out an appropriate trade-off.

In the batch of experiments that follows, we vary the support threshold in
the [0.1, 1.0] range and report the number of rules generated from the *TFM-2009*
465 dataset. Figure 1, *left plot*, presents the results. From the Figure we observe that
TFM-2009 exhibits a skewed support distribution, as the majority of association
rules have low support while the remaining ones have high support. From the
same plot, we also observe a clear distinction in the number of rules generated
when the support threshold is greater or equal than 0.3, indicating that lower
470 values yield the generation of many irrelevant rules – we report that similar
results were obtained when considering the *TFM-2010* and *TFM-2011* datasets.

Figure 1: Analysis on the distributions of *support* and *confidence* when generating association rules from the *TFM-2009* dataset. *Left plot*: Support distribution. *Right plot*: confidence distribution (support threshold is set to 0.3).

Finally, we report that using a support threshold smaller or equal than 0.3 allows us to generate association rules involving all the features of the datasets.

In the next batch of experiments we study how varying the confidence threshold affects the generation of association rules. To this end, we set *support* = 0.3 and vary the confidence in the [0.1, 1.0] range. The dataset considered is, again, *TFM-2009*. From Figure 1, *right plot*, we observe that variations in *confidence* have minor effects on the number of generated rules. We also report that using confidence values smaller or equal than 0.6 yield association rules that involve all the features present in the dataset. We report that similar results were achieved with the *TFM-2010* and *TFM-2011* datasets.

In the final batch of experiments we study how varying the lift threshold affects the generation of association rules. To this end we set *support* to 0.3, *confidence* to 0.6, and vary *lift* in the [1.0, 6.0] range. The datasets considered are *TFM-2009*, *TFM-2010*, and *TFM-2011*. Figure 2 presents the results. From the plots we see that increasing lift has the effect of reducing the number of generated rules, with the surviving rules exhibiting high correlation between pairs of features – note that this trend holds for all the datasets. Finally, we report that using lift values smaller or equal than 1.3 entails the generation of association rules that involve all the features available in the datasets.

In light of the above findings, in the batches of experiments that follow we always set *support* to 0.3, *confidence* to 0.6, and *lift* to 1.3.

Figure 2: Distribution of *lift*. *support* is set to 0.3. *confidence* is set to 0.6.

5.2. Analysis on ALICIA’s run-time performance

In this study we analyze ALICIA’s run-time performance. We focus on phase
 495 III (Section 3.3, Algorithm 4), as the cost of phase I is dictated by the temporal
 complexity of Apriori Agrawal & Srikant (1994) while the cost of phase II is
 negligible. During the third phase there are two parameters that affect ALICIA’s
 performance: the threshold on the maximum number of features associated with
 a vertex, *maxFeatsVertex*, and the *n*-reachability threshold. In the first batch
 500 of experiments we focus on *maxFeatsVertex* and vary it in the [1,14] range
 when considering the TFM-2009 and TFM-2010 datasets, while we use the
 [1,16] range when considering the TFM-2011 dataset. All the other parameters
 are set to their respective defaults (Section 4.4). Figure 3 reports the results.

From the results we observe that *maxFeatsVertex* noticeably impacts ALI-
 505 CIA’s execution time, with increasing running times as *maxFeatsVertex* be-
 comes larger. We also report, however, that the F-measure scores achieved
 by the SVM-based classifier did not exhibit considerable variations between
maxFeatsVertex = 1 and *maxFeatsVertex* = 6, thus indicating that the ex-
 ecution time can be safely reduced by setting *maxFeatsVertex* appropriately

Figure 3: ALICIA’s phase III execution time when varying the $maxFeatsVertex$ parameter. The datasets considered are *TFM-2009*, *TFM-2010*, and *TFM-2011*.

510 (and according to the characteristics of the dataset considered). We finally note that the maximum value $maxFeatsVertex$ could assume during the experiments was 6, as this represents the length of the longest rules produced by phase I.

In the second batch of experiments we focus on the n -reachability threshold. 515 To this end we vary this parameter in the $[1, 50]$ range, while setting the other ones to their respective defaults (Section 4.4). We consider the same datasets used in the previous evaluation. From the results (Figure 4) we observe that ALICIA’s execution time increases linearly, and that the performance difference between the lowest ($n = 1$) and the highest ($n = 50$) values does not exceed 3 520 seconds. Overall, we argue that the n -reachability threshold has a very limited impact on ALICIA’s performance.

5.3. Analysis on the quality of feature selection

In this section we assess the quality of the results produced by ALICIA and perform a comparison with its competitors. To this end we perform two different 525 studies: in the first one we analyze how variations in the n -reachability threshold affect ALICIA’s feature selection quality. The second study performs a thorough

Figure 4: ALICIA’s phase III execution time when varying the n -reachability threshold. Y-axis is associated with the execution time (sec.), while X-axis is associated with n . The datasets considered are *TFM-2009*, *TFM-2010*, and *TFM-2011*.

comparison among several feature selection methods.

5.3.1. Varying the n -reachability parameter

In the first batch of experiments we study how the choice of the n -reachability
 530 parameter used with the F2TI centrality measure affects the quality of the
 results returned by ALICIA. To this end we consider all the three datasets and
 vary n in the $[1, 50]$ range. For each value assigned to n we consider the ranking
 produced by F2TI and incrementally include the features, starting from the most
 relevant ones: the subset of features yielding the best F-Measure determines the
 535 F-Measure shown in the plots. For what concerns support, confidence, and lift,
 we set them to their defaults (Section 4.4). Figure 5 present the results.

From the plots we observe how increasing the n -reachability threshold im-
 proves the F-Measure achieved by ALICIA until $n \leq 10$, while using larger values
 do not yield further performance gains. This indicates that $n = 10$ represents
 540 the best trade-off between quality of results and time took to execute F2TI. As
 such, in the batches of experiments that follow we set $n = 10$.

Figure 5: Analysis on the quality of results when varying the n -reachability within the F2TI measure. Y-axis is associated with F-Measure, while X-axis is associated with n . The datasets considered are *TFM-2009*, *TFM-2010*, and *TFM-2011*.

5.3.2. Competitors comparison

In the batch of experiments that follows we compare the quality of the results between ALICIA and its competitors. To this end we consider all the datasets previously introduced, i.e., *TFM-2009*, *TFM-2010*, and *TFM-2011*. We set the n -reachability threshold to 10, while support, confidence, and lift are set to their respective defaults (Section 4.4). The features considered by the various competitors are chosen according to the ranking produced by F2TI – more precisely, features are incrementally included starting from the most relevant ones. The quality of the results is assessed by means of the F-Measure achieved by the SVM classifier. Tables 2, 3, and 4 report the results.

From the tables we observe that ALICIA almost always outperforms its competitors. More precisely, ALICIA achieves the best results with *TFM-2009* when the number of considered features is equal to 5 (the resulting F-Measure is equal to 72%). Similarly, ALICIA achieves the best results with *TFM-2010* and *TFM-2011* when the number of considered features is, respectively, equal to 5 and 6, with the resulting F-Measure scores equal to 73% and 77%.

top feats	IG	GR	CFS	ECFS	RELIEF-F	FISHER	GBFS	ALICIA
14	0.5838	0.5838	0.5838	0.5838	0.5838	0.5838	0.5838	0.5838
13	0.5965	0.5519	0.5937	0.5419	0.5762	0.5647	0.5826	0.6068
12	0.6113	0.5766	0.5878	0.6278	0.5015	0.5314	0.5581	0.6171
11	0.6027	0.5885	0.5582	0.6422	0.5552	0.5895	0.6418	0.6363
10	0.5885	0.4737	0.5497	0.4372	0.5381	0.6243	0.6546	0.6508
9	0.5458	0.5769	0.5026	0.4401	0.5663	0.6512	0.6398	0.6449
8	0.5671	0.5924	0.5364	0.4698	0.5332	0.6785	0.6581	0.6632
7	0.5671	0.5956	0.6088	0.5942	0.4707	0.6213	0.6006	0.6723
6	0.5856	0.6130	0.5322	0.5176	0.5645	0.5819	0.5675	0.6956
5	0.6374	0.6001	0.5508	0.5044	0.5476	0.5512	0.6247	0.7172
4	0.5261	0.6022	0.4918	0.4873	0.4879	0.5416	0.5051	0.6975
3	0.6251	0.4904	0.5875	0.4691	0.4261	0.5318	0.6001	0.6661
2	0.5844	0.4114	0.5456	0.4182	0.4368	0.5115	0.5786	0.5938
1	0.4717	0.4047	0.4426	0.4102	0.4061	0.4811	0.4623	0.4966

Table 2: Analysis on the quality of feature selection, **TFM-2009** dataset. The column **top feats** illustrates the number of *top* features selected from the ranking produced by the various feature selection algorithms. Each figure within the other columns represents the F-measure achieved by the SVM-based classifier when using the ranking produced by the associated feature selection method. Winners are highlighted in **bold**.

top feats	IG	GR	CFS	ECFS	RELIEF-F	Fisher	GBFS	ALICIA
14	0.5868	0.5868	0.5868	0.5868	0.5868	0.5868	0.5868	0.5868
13	0.6468	0.6359	0.6189	0.4245	0.5584	0.5803	0.6515	0.6485
12	0.6355	0.6429	0.6220	0.5916	0.5848	0.6092	0.6496	0.6434
11	0.6277	0.6236	0.6273	0.5515	0.6512	0.5483	0.6292	0.6342
10	0.6253	0.6164	0.6148	0.4749	0.6348	0.5715	0.6108	0.6297
9	0.6514	0.6513	0.6427	0.4563	0.4302	0.6424	0.6371	0.6599
8	0.6548	0.6607	0.6406	0.5202	0.4743	0.6281	0.6316	0.6784
7	0.6592	0.6512	0.6414	0.5422	0.4621	0.6103	0.6295	0.6961
6	0.6362	0.6560	0.6396	0.5214	0.5139	0.6202	0.6201	0.7006
5	0.5828	0.6499	0.6545	0.4573	0.6018	0.6099	0.5915	0.7291
4	0.5736	0.5919	0.5816	0.4084	0.4456	0.5893	0.5730	0.7044
3	0.5963	0.5906	0.5803	0.4150	0.4650	0.5708	0.5879	0.7029
2	0.6081	0.5912	0.5831	0.4288	0.4078	0.5691	0.5718	0.6956
1	0.5301	0.5228	0.5159	0.4824	0.5049	0.5681	0.5477	0.5915

Table 3: Analysis on the quality of feature selection, **TFM-2010** dataset.

In the second batch of experiments we compare ALICIA against the GBFS algorithm. Although GBFS belongs to the class of wrapper methods, we consider it in the experimental evaluation as it is the state-of-the-art in feature selec-

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top feats	IG	GR	CFS	ECFS	RELIEF-F	Fisher	GBFS	ALICIA
16	0.5534	0.5534	0.5534	0.5534	0.5534	0.5534	0.5534	0.5534
15	0.5893	0.5579	0.5452	0.5854	0.5493	0.5667	0.5957	0.5905
14	0.5765	0.5982	0.528	0.6105	0.5431	0.5265	0.6614	0.6501
13	0.6481	0.6086	0.5961	0.6201	0.6210	0.5542	0.6221	0.6199
12	0.5945	0.5572	0.5519	0.5389	0.5637	0.5422	0.6016	0.5824
11	0.6084	0.6683	0.5486	0.5482	0.6000	0.5406	0.6227	0.6937
10	0.5805	0.6315	0.5258	0.6088	0.5457	0.5217	0.5929	0.6724
9	0.6523	0.6591	0.5915	0.5783	0.6099	0.5328	0.6212	0.6877
8	0.6264	0.6832	0.5702	0.5345	0.5231	0.5638	0.5913	0.6948
7	0.6671	0.6004	0.6025	0.5227	0.5239	0.5656	0.6418	0.7023
6	0.6608	0.6706	0.6111	0.6339	0.5428	0.5115	0.6463	0.7688
5	0.6433	0.6634	0.6119	0.5436	0.6273	0.5583	0.6235	0.7534
4	0.6709	0.6976	0.5937	0.6284	0.5819	0.5124	0.6451	0.7468
3	0.6002	0.5752	0.5491	0.6015	0.5986	0.5244	0.5833	0.7260
2	0.6046	0.6089	0.5588	0.6068	0.5250	0.5576	0.5798	0.7211
1	0.4987	0.4915	0.4611	0.5157	0.6091	0.5144	0.5055	0.5421

Table 4: Analysis on the quality of feature selection, **TFM-2011** dataset.

tion. In order to obtain the best result with GBFS we conducted a grid search according to the following parameter ranges: $learningrate = [0.01, 0.05, 0.1]$, $depth = [4, 5, 6]$, $ntrees = [100, 200, 300, 400]$. We report that GBFS achieved the best results with the following combination: $learningrate = 0.05$, $depth = 5$,
565 $ntrees = 200$. To analyze ALICIA’s ability to generalize to other types of dataset, we compare it with the competitors over an unbalanced dataset, i.e., *DS-CreditCard*. In this analysis we included an over-comparison method, the XGBoost Feature Importance (XGB-FI); this is a necessary requirement as the library we employ to implement GBFS (i.e., Python XGBoost) uses natively
570 XGB-FI within the classifier. Table 5 presents the results achieved by the competitors. From the results we observe that ALICIA achieves the best classification result when the number of considered features is equal to 25 (the resulting F-Measure is equal to 89.13%) and that it outperforms its competitors.

6. Related work

575 Fawcett and Provost [Fawcett & Provost \(1997\)](#) present a technique to detect frauds involving cloning of mobile phones. In their work the authors employs

a single layer perceptron network coupled with a feature selection technique called *sequential forward selection process* Kittler (1986). In the experimental evaluation the authors show that their method greatly reduces the number of features (i.e., from 198 to 11) while allowing to achieve 92% of accuracy. Finally,

top feats	IG	GR	XGB-FI	CFS	ECFS	RELIEF-F	Fisher	GBFS	ALICIA
30	0.8696	0.8696	0.8696	0.8696	0.8696	0.8696	0.8696	0.8696	0.8696
29	0.8663	0.8663	0.8663	0.8649	0.8696	0.8710	0.8663	0.8649	0.8743
28	0.8710	0.8710	0.8865	0.8268	0.8649	0.8710	0.8710	0.8757	0.8865
27	0.8466	0.8617	0.8770	0.8161	0.8649	0.8710	0.8617	0.8757	0.8865
26	0.8571	0.8617	0.8663	0.8315	0.8541	0.8710	0.8602	0.8804	0.8865
25	0.8571	0.8617	0.8663	0.8202	0.8710	0.8710	0.8602	0.8663	0.8913
24	0.8511	0.8617	0.8723	0.8268	0.8462	0.8757	0.8663	0.8511	0.8427
23	0.8723	0.8466	0.8663	0.8268	0.8444	0.8757	0.8602	0.8710	0.8315
22	0.8723	0.8757	0.8617	0.8380	0.8444	0.8617	0.8757	0.8696	0.8380
21	0.8723	0.8710	0.8723	0.8444	0.8444	0.8617	0.8852	0.8710	0.8492
20	0.8632	0.8617	0.8571	0.8427	0.8444	0.8511	0.8696	0.8587	0.8380
19	0.8663	0.8663	0.8360	0.8398	0.8462	0.8466	0.8830	0.8757	0.8398
18	0.8617	0.8663	0.8360	0.8242	0.8444	0.8617	0.8770	0.8770	0.8539
17	0.8511	0.8602	0.8404	0.8398	0.8539	0.8387	0.8770	0.8617	0.8603
16	0.8449	0.8649	0.8387	0.8370	0.8427	0.8324	0.8617	0.8649	0.8619
15	0.8387	0.8817	0.8298	0.8495	0.8475	0.8541	0.8541	0.8602	0.8539
14	0.8280	0.8757	0.8404	0.8495	0.8475	0.8541	0.8602	0.8663	0.8588
13	0.8404	0.8791	0.8360	0.8649	0.8475	0.8541	0.8710	0.8723	0.8603
12	0.8556	0.8602	0.8449	0.8352	0.8475	0.8541	0.8587	0.8663	0.8556
11	0.8602	0.8511	0.8449	0.8333	0.8588	0.8602	0.8587	0.8602	0.8619
10	0.8415	0.8415	0.8495	0.8380	0.8556	0.8696	0.8398	0.8495	0.8556
9	0.8478	0.8462	0.8556	0.8333	0.8352	0.8541	0.8404	0.8495	0.8462
8	0.8432	0.8587	0.8602	0.8023	0.8045	0.8743	0.8478	0.8525	0.8398
7	0.8197	0.8148	0.8634	0.8023	0.8043	0.8696	0.8432	0.8619	0.8508
6	0.8202	0.7568	0.8541	0.7126	0.7778	0.8478	0.8370	0.8360	0.8045
5	0.8085	0.7708	0.8462	0.6857	0.7869	0.8387	0.8387	0.8085	0.8045
4	0.8085	0.7813	0.8132	0.6826	0.5867	0.8235	0.7979	0.8085	0.8156
3	0.7937	0.7857	0.8415	0.0594	0.5503	0.8415	0.7514	0.7937	0.8068
2	0.7486	0.7449	0.7351	0.0000	0.2414	0.7351	0.6429	0.7486	0.7174
1	0.6882	0.6882	0.6023	0.0000	0.0000	0.6023	0.6000	0.6882	0.6000

Table 5: Analysis on the quality of feature selection, *DS-CreditCard* dataset. The column **top feats** illustrates the number of *top* features selected from the ranking produced by the various feature selection algorithms. Each figure within the other columns represents the F-measure achieved by the XGB classifier when using the ranking produced by the associated feature selection method. Winners are highlighted in **bold**.

the authors report non-negligible misclassification costs.

In [Yang & Hwang \(2006\)](#) Yang and Hwang propose an approach to detect frauds perpetrated in the health-care domain. The approach works by building a detection model from clinical pathways, where features are based on frequent control-flow patterns inferred from two datasets – one containing fraudulent instances while the other one containing regular instances. They then use a probability framework based on the Markov blanket filter to perform feature selection, which allows to reduce the number of features from 30,701 to 3,120. The experimental evaluation shows that their approach is capable of identifying several fraudulent cases that cannot be detected by manually constructed detection models, and that the use of feature selection increases accuracy from 40% to 69%.

Similarly, [Li et al. \(2008\)](#) provides a comprehensive survey of statistical methods used to detect frauds perpetrated in health-care. Here, the authors point out how feature selection plays a very important role in this domain, yet most of the literature omit discussing the details behind the engineering of features due to legal issues and privacy concerns.

In [Kotsiantis et al. \(2006\)](#) the authors explore the ability of machine learning techniques to detect companies issuing fraudulent financial statements. In this work the authors employ a feature selection method that ranks the relevance of features according to a statistical measure called *ReliefF*. ReliefF determines the relevance of each feature according to its ability in disambiguating *similar* samples, where the notion of similarity is expressed in terms of *proximity* within the feature space. In the experimental evaluation the authors show how ReliefF reduces the set of considered features from 25 to 8 features. The authors compare also several machine learning techniques, i.e., C4.5, RBF, Bayesian Networks, KNN, and SVM, and show that C4.5 achieves the best results by correctly classifying the 85.2% of fraudulent cases, the 93.3% of non-fraudulent cases, and the 91.2% of cases in the validation sets.

[Belhadji et al. \(2000\)](#) propose an approach to pick up fraud features deemed to be the most significant when predicting the probability that a claim is fraud-

ulent. The approach is structured in three phases: first, their approach takes in
input a set of fraud features provided by selected domain experts. Secondly, for
each feature the approach calculates the associated conditional probability. Fi-
nally, the approach leverages *Probit regression* to determine the most significant
features.

7. Conclusions

In this work we propose a novel feature selection method, ALICIA, that
leverages association rules, propositional logic, and a carefully crafted graph
centrality measure to improve the detection of potential tax fraudsters. To
assess the validity of ALICIA we conduct an extensive experimental evaluation,
where we compare our proposal with other eight well-established methods, i.e.,
information gain, gain ratio, correlation-based feature selection, feature selection
via eigenvector centrality, RELIEF-F, Fisher, and Gradient Boosted Feature
Selection. The evaluation is conducted by employing an SVM-based classifier
on three real-world datasets provided by the treasury office of the state of Ceará
(SEFAZ-CE).

The findings of this study have to be seen in light of some limitations. First,
the lack of available and/or reliable data from different tax administrations
makes a more comprehensive comparison of our results difficult. We deal with
this limitation by using datasets from different periods of time, i.e., 2009, 2010
and 2011. We also use a credit card dataset provided by Kaggle, which demon-
strates the ability of ALICIA to generalize to different kinds of frauds. Second,
the lack of prior research studies on the topic limits the scope of our analysis.
We overcome this limitation by utilizing the expertise of business experts from
the Treasury Office of the State of Ceará (SEFAZ-CE - Brazil), as well as the
knowledge from prior studies on fraud detection in other domains. Finally, due
to security constraints that could expose tax fraud identification techniques, we
could not disclose the characteristics of fraud indicators (features), which in
turn has the potential to limit the ability to explain the results achieved in this

work. We overcame this issue by clearly describing the type of tax frauds considered in this work (i.e., frauds involving Circulation of Goods and Transport Services).

Lessons learned. First, we experimentally show that ALICIA consistently outperforms its competitors by achieving the best F-Measure scores for the *TFM-2009* (71.71%), *TFM-2010* (72.91%), *TFM-2011* (76.88%) and *DS-creditcard* (89.13%) datasets, thus demonstrating ALICIA’s superiority in providing appropriate subsets of features to classification methods. Subsequently, we confirm that ALICIA provides consistent results over time, thus proving its resilience to changes in the set of considered features. Finally, we show how well ALICIA generalizes in the fraud domain. To this end we consider the credit card dataset provided by Kaggle, and use an XGB classifier: the results show that ALICIA outperforms its competitors with F-measure scores up to 89.13%.

Future work. We plan to work on a distributed version of ALICIA, as existing literature show that centrality measures can be implemented by means of the Map Reduce paradigm [Kang et al. \(2011\)](#); [Lerman et al. \(2010\)](#). We believe this has the potential to benefit the scalability of our approach, and thus make ALICIA a “building block” of domain-specific intelligent systems and applications. We also plan to analyze how ALICIA performs with different propositional logic argument forms, e.g., conjunction, addition, and simplification. Finally, we aim at addressing the *Link Prediction* problem [Al Hasan & Zaki \(2011\)](#), i.e., predicting the likelihood of future associations between seemingly unrelated subsets of features. To this end we intend to analyze how association rules change over time, what are the factors that determine the rules, and how associations between subsets of features can be possibly influenced by other subsets of features.

Implications of the study. The findings from the experimental evaluation show how ALICIA addresses the study’s research questions and achieve the overall goal of selecting the most appropriate subset of binary features to improve potential tax fraudsters classification. These findings have some significant implications. The first one stems from the observation that ALICIA represents a new effective approach to discover tax fraudsters, thus benefiting the fight

against tax evasion and the society in general. Secondly, ALICIA leverages the structural properties behind graphs of association rules to determine the most relevant fraud indicators. Finally, observe that the centrality measure introduced in this work can be employed in other domains, as the measure solely focus on structural properties of graphs.

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